

COMPOSITE SAMPLING FOR TOXICS
IN DRINKING WATER

GREAT LAKES PROTECTION FUND PROJECT FG6901064

FINAL REPORT

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PART 1: GRANT REPORT

1. Regional action to enhance the health of the Great Lakes ecosystem.

We presume that the health of the Great Lakes ecosystem is understood to include the health of its human population, which is the focus of this project. By design, this project is limited to the Lake Erie basin, but is a prototype of an approach to sampling for toxics which could be applied throughout the basin, and for that matter, outside the basin as well.

This project has **identified** concerns about exposure to pesticides and other toxic substances as a major issue within the Great Lakes ecosystem, including (but not limited to) exposure via drinking water drawn from the Great Lakes, processed at municipal water treatment facilities, and delivered to Great Lakes citizens for consumption. At the beginning of the project, there were little or no data to validate or refute these concerns.

The project has **identified** a possible point source of metolachlor in the vicinity of Monroe, Michigan. Identification of this possible point source is based on the repeated presence of metolachlor in the Monroe samples, at concentrations not seen at any other station, and at times of year when runoff of metolachlor from the land is unlikely. The identity of this compound was verified in several samples by GC/MS analysis.

This project has **demonstrated** that composite sampling at public water supply plants is a relatively inexpensive, reliable way to obtain average concentration data which reflect human exposures to toxics through drinking water, provided that the compounds of interest are stable under storage during the compositing period. It has demonstrated the feasibility of accumulating a composite sample both using automated samplers and using public water supply personnel to obtain the aliquots. It has demonstrated that, for stable compounds, the composite concentration is not substantially different from the average of concentrations in daily samples, but can be obtained at an analytical cost about 1/30 as great, since only one analysis per per station per month is needed. At stations subject to extensive temporal variability (particularly river stations) composite sampling may offer the only way to obtain exposure concentrations which are both representative and affordable. *Composite sampling has been shown to be an important, cost-effective tool which can be used in the ongoing effort to identify and evaluate threats to the Great Lakes ecosystem.*

The project has also **demonstrated** that herbicide concentrations in Lake Erie are consistently well below the lifetime health advisory levels for these compounds, and that consequently there is no health risk to the human population which utilizes Lake Erie drinking

water, due to herbicide exposures through drinking water. The results of the project also suggest, but do not prove, that herbicide concentrations in Lake Erie are below thresholds for aquatic ecosystem effects. Since the herbicides studied are among the most heavily used in the Great Lakes basin, and since their health advisory levels are among the lowest of these pesticides, this study has demonstrated that, in terms of the currently known adverse effects, *herbicide concentrations deriving from non-point (agricultural) sources are not a toxic threat to the Great Lakes ecosystem or to the citizens of the Great Lakes basin.*

The project has **demonstrated** that atrazine is stable under refrigerated storage for periods of time exceeding two months, but that alachlor breaks down to a substantial degree during this period of time. This means that composite sampling for atrazine can use a monthly compositing interval, but analyses of the same samples for alachlor will produce concentrations which are biased low.

This project has **promoted** the concept of composite sampling and awareness of the project itself, through mailings and phone calls to state and federal EPAs, the International Joint Commission, and other interested parties; and through inclusion of the project in descriptions of the work of the WQL in numerous talks given to both technical and non-technical audiences, and in publications such as our annual report. A presentation devoted to the results of the study was given at the June 1993 meetings of the International Association for Great Lakes Research. This presentation led to interviews with the staff of the Wisconsin Sea Grant program, subsequent descriptions of the project and its results in the Wisconsin Sea Grant newsletter, and possible future use of portions of the interview on an environmentally oriented program on Wisconsin Public Radio. The scientific portion of the project final report will be disseminated to all water treatment plant cooperators, and to appropriate offices of state, regional, and national EPAs. One or two papers will be prepared for publication in the peer-reviewed scientific literature.

2. Problems and solutions

The problems encountered have been minor for the most part. One treatment plant was reluctant to commit the minimal staff time to take the daily aliquots; this problem was solved by installing an automatic sampler at that site. A second treatment plant was reluctant to participate at all, partly because they had already participated in a similar study and felt they had nothing to gain from our study. Because this plant was in a crucial part of the basin, and served a large municipality, we were unwilling to omit it from the study. This problem was solved by recruiting a person within the distribution network of that plant to collect samples for us. The first cooperator was found to be unreliable about taking the desired samples, and was replaced by

another volunteer, who maintained a sampling record which was among the best among all the stations.

We encountered a problem with sending samples and sampling containers back and forth from Canadian stations, due to the high and unpredictable costs charged by courier companies going across the border. This problem was never really solved; some budget adjustments allowed the cost overruns to be minimized. In addition, the red tape involved in getting the samples across the border often led to increased shipping times. While these problems were significant in the scope of our project, they are not inherent in composite sampling, and could be managed with proper planning in an ongoing composite-based monitoring program for toxics.

The major problem encountered is that we did not receive much indication of interest in our project from the state and federal officials who should be the initial beneficiaries of the results of this study. The original plan for dissemination of information from the project included a workshop for these officials at some central location. It became apparent that, between institutional inertia and lack of support for travel, such a workshop would not be successful. This left a gap in our dissemination plans. We have sought to fill that gap through our presentation at the IAGLR meetings and the subsequent interviews; through publication of our results, probably in the *Journal of Great Lakes Research*; through news releases describing our results; and by sending copies of our final report to these agencies. None the less, it is clear that simply creating a reasonable dissemination plan does not guarantee that valid and useful scientific results will be translated into institutional practices.

3. Lessons learned

- Composite sampling is an effective approach for characterizing average concentrations.
- A monthly compositing interval is feasible for atrazine, but too long for alachlor, if the composite sample is stored under refrigeration. Some means of preventing alachlor breakdown is needed if alachlor is to be monitored successfully by a monthly compositing program.
- Public water supply personnel are generally interested in the quality of their water, and are willing to participate in research projects which help to define water quality. Direct personal contact with the cooperators helps to maintain their interest in the project, and to assure consistent performance in obtaining the daily aliquots.
- Automatic samplers can be adapted for reliable use in a composite sampling program.

- Institutional fragmentation and inertia can be major impediments to the adoption of innovations which could improve our ability to manage the Great Lakes ecosystem effectively, even within the institutions whose mission it is to do so. As one agricultural scientist said at a recent meeting, "Bureaucracy is the epoxy which greases the wheels of government!" Environmental managers should eagerly seek out new technologies which will help them do a better job of management, but in many cases their motivation is more oriented to maintaining the status quo.

- To an alarming degree, environmental policy in the United States is being driven by interest groups, the politics of popular belief, distorted and polarized media statements, and not a little creative fearmongering. Objective scientific information frequently is either used selectively to support a non-objective position, or ignored completely.

PART 2: SCIENTIFIC REPORT

INTRODUCTION

In the Great Lakes basin, more than 10 million people derive their drinking water from sources in the Great Lakes. In Ohio alone, 2.5 million people drink Lake Erie water. Drinking water represents the major pathway by which some toxic substances enter the human body, and an important secondary pathway for many others. While some individuals engage in activities which may involve more important pathways for some toxics (e.g. occupational exposures to farmers and industrial workers, or consumption of certain Great Lakes fish by recreational fishermen), everyone drinks water, and everyone whose water supply is the Great Lakes is exposed involuntarily to the toxics contained in that water.

In almost all cases, the potential hazard from exposure to toxic substances is chronic rather than acute, because concentrations high enough to cause acute effects are rarely encountered in the waters of the Great Lakes. Chronic exposures can lead to cancer, and to other health effects such as reproductive impairment, mutations, behavioral effects, and impairment of organ and immune systems. Generally, these effects either involve a long latency period or accumulate over a long period of time. Accurate assessment of the risks of such health effects requires accurate information on the average concentrations of these compounds in drinking water, to which people are exposed over a long period of time.

Monitoring for many of these toxic substances in drinking water is not mandated, or else the required monitoring is insufficient to provide an accurate picture of the average concentrations. The U.S. EPA currently requires analysis of four or fewer samples per year for the compounds listed in Table 1, part 1. Many compounds which are known to cause adverse health effects are not on this list, and many of the compounds which are on the list are rarely if ever detected in drinking water. Most water treatment plants do not voluntarily sample more frequently than required, or perform analyses for non-mandatory compounds, because the analyses are costly, and many require expertise not available in-house. Thus our working knowledge of the exposure rates to toxics through drinking water is either non-existent, or is based on only one sample per year.

Implementation during 1993 of the 1986 amendment to the Safe Drinking Water Act has increased sampling frequency to from annual to quarterly, and requires analysis of the compounds listed in Table 1, parts 1 and 2 (Pontius, 1990). While this will represent an improvement over the current situation, even four samples per year are inadequate to accurately characterize human exposure rates, particularly where water sources are subject to rapid and unpredictable fluctuations in concentration.

Table 1. Compounds mandated for analysis in drinking water supplies (organics only)

Part 1. National Interim Public Drinking Water Regulations compounds		
2,4,5-TP (Silvex)	2,4-D	Lindane
Toxaphene	Methoxychlor	Endrin
	Trihalomethanes	
Part 2. Safe Drinking Water Act Amendment compounds		
Alachlor	Atrazine	Aldicarb
Carbofuran	Glyphosate	Simazine
Metolachlor*	Metribuzin*	

* Listed as a priority compound but not mandated at present.

Water intakes for the communities which use Great Lakes water are generally close to the shores of the lakes, where most pollutants are found in the greatest and most variable concentrations. In addition, many toxic substances, particularly those of non-point origin, have a seasonal component to their concentrations, and are washed into the lakes by tributary storm runoff. Although mixing of the tributary influents with the lake water decreases the range of concentrations, substantial fluctuations in concentration do occur in the nearshore zones of the lakes, where most water treatment plant intakes are located. Periods of high wave action can resuspend bottom sediments in the nearshore zone, releasing toxics (including dissolved phases) held in the sediment. Because of these systematic (seasonal) and random (storm impact, wave resuspension) variations in concentration, one sample or even four samples cannot give an accurate picture of toxics exposure through drinking water.

Daily samples would resolve all but the most short-term fluctuations in concentration, and these rapid fluctuations are not likely to be of great magnitude. Thus a daily sampling program would provide abundant information to characterize the average concentrations to which consumers of Great Lakes water are exposed. A daily sampling program would be prohibitively expensive, however, primarily due to the expense of the chemical analyses involved. Even a weekly sampling program would be prohibitively expensive, yet it would not be frequent enough to resolve some spikes of concentration associated with storm runoff from tributaries, or with sediment resuspension events in the nearshore zone. Thus the dilemma is that typical current sampling programs give an inadequate indication of human exposures to toxics, but adequate sampling programs are prohibitively expensive.

A possible solution to this dilemma lies in uncoupling the water sampling process from the chemical analysis. For toxic substances which are chronic health risks, the short-term

fluctuations in exposure concentrations have no direct health implications. They are only a confounding factor in obtaining an accurate exposure concentration. Thus, if samples of equal volume are taken daily and added together for a period of time, and the composite sample is then analyzed, the concentration in the composite sample is, in principle, identical to the average concentration one would have obtained if each daily sample were analyzed separately. The averaging is done physically, by compositing the samples, rather than mathematically. Statistical information about the short-term fluctuations (variance) in concentration is lost, but this information is not important for exposure assessment. Compositing samples for a month would provide concentrations as accurate as a daily sampling program, but at little more than 1/30 the cost.

Project Goals and Objectives

The goal of this project was to operate and evaluate a prototype monitoring program for toxics exposure through drinking water, using composite samples in the manner just described. The program obtained samples from the thirteen Lake Erie water treatment systems shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The sampling locations

We choose atrazine and alachlor as the target chemicals for the following reasons:

1. The U.S. EPA has set maximum contaminant levels for drinking water for alachlor of 2.0 ppb and for atrazine of 3.0 ppb. In Great Lakes tributaries draining agricultural lands, time

weighted annual average concentrations approach these levels, and monthly average concentrations generally exceed these levels during May, June, and July. Thus waters entering the Great Lakes are carrying concentrations of these substances comparable to those identified as unacceptable for chronic exposure.

2. Alachlor is classified by the U.S. EPA as a probable human carcinogen; atrazine is classified as a possible human carcinogen. The Human Health Effects Committee of the International Joint Commission has expressed concern about possible human health impacts of alachlor, and called for further surveillance and assessment (IJC, 1986).
3. These compounds are found in water primarily in the dissolved state, and are therefore more likely to be passed into finished drinking water than more strongly sediment-bound toxics.
4. These compounds are less persistent than many other toxics, and thus are more likely to be affected by storage before analysis. Their concentrations are also seasonal in nature, and strongly affected by storm runoff. A monitoring program which deals successfully with the problems posed by these compounds should also be successful with other more stable toxics.
5. These compounds are widely used throughout the agricultural portions of the Great Lakes watershed. In the Ohio drainage basin of Lake Erie, for which recent detailed data are available, over 1450 tons (active ingredient) of alachlor and over 850 tons (active ingredient) of atrazine were applied in 1986 (Waldron, 1989). Alachlor and atrazine together constitute nearly 45% of the tonnage, and more than 75% of the "toxic load" of pesticides applied to row crop agriculture in Ohio (Baker and Richards, 1991). Analogous figures for the entire Great Lakes basin are not available, but are likely to be comparable. Unlike many toxic substances, pesticides are of non-point origin, and are found generally in rivers throughout the Great Lakes basin (Thurman et al., 1991; Bodo, 1991).
6. Because of our extensive work on the behavior of these compounds in the Great Lakes basin, we know better what behavior to expect of them than we do of other toxics of more localized occurrence.

We choose Lake Erie as the prototype program's phase 1 site for the following reasons:

1. Its drainage basin has the most heavily agricultural land use of the five lakes. Thus it is most likely to be the one where pesticide exposures through drinking water are a problem.
2. Lake Erie's tributaries are, as a group, the most variable in flow and concentrations over time periods of days to weeks. A toxics monitoring program which works for Lake Erie should be adequate for the other lakes as well.
3. Of the Great Lakes, Lake Erie serves as a drinking water source for the largest U.S. population, with the exception of Lake Michigan.
4. Lake Erie is most conveniently located to our laboratory, and is the lake with which we have the greatest experience.

The objectives of the project were four:

1. To evaluate the composite sampling technique as a means of obtaining accurate average concentrations of the target compounds.
2. To evaluate the reliability of water treatment plant operators as local cooperators who would take the composite samples for us.
3. To explore possible losses of the target pesticides during storage under refrigeration.
4. To obtain initial estimates of exposures to pesticides through drinking water taken from Lake Erie.

METHODS

Sampling

Composite sampling

The main composite sampling program served both to evaluate operator reliability and to estimate drinking water exposures to pesticides through finished tap water derived from Lake Erie.

Composite samples of finished drinking water were collected in 4 Liter brown glass bottles (empty pesticide-grade solvent bottles) which were kept under refrigeration. Samples were taken in the water treatment plant with one exception: the Toledo plant declined to participate in the study, so local volunteers who received their water from the Toledo plant's distribution stream were enlisted to obtain the Toledo samples. Compositing was performed by water treatment personnel in all cases except at the Monroe, Michigan plant, where an automatic sampler was installed and programmed to take the daily sample, and in Toledo, where local volunteers were used. Daily aliquots of 100 mL were collected from a finished water tap in teflon beakers, and added to the accumulating composite sample in the glass bottle, which was kept capped between additions of daily aliquots. Due to differences in weekend work patterns among plants, samples were not obtained at all plants on Saturdays and Sundays. Thus the composite sample could be based on five, six, or seven aliquots per week, depending on the plant work schedule.

At the end of each month, composite samples were delivered to the Water Quality Laboratory (WQL), where they were processed for analysis. WQL personnel picked up samples at plants between Monroe, Michigan and Cleveland, Ohio. Samples from more distant locations were sent by second-day air. Another composite sample container was either delivered in person or shipped to the plant in time to be available at the beginning of each month. Two grams of sodium thiosulfate were added to the glass bottles before use each month, in order to reduce to chloride any free chlorine, which would otherwise combine with some of the pesticide present, and cause a low bias in the measured concentrations.

Calendars were provided to each cooperator, and the cooperators were asked to mark off each day when a sample was taken. The monthly calendar sheet was included with the sample, to provide data on the consistency with which scheduled aliquots were taken. Every effort was made to assure the cooperators that no stigma was attached to missing a sample, and that honest recording of the calendar was more important than appearing to be perfect.

Sampling to evaluate compositing

During 1991, samples were composited from daily 100 mL aliquots at the WQL's Rock Creek station, located on the Heidelberg College campus, using an autosampler. The compositing pattern thus matched that being used in the Lake Erie water treatment plants. The basic compositing interval was weekly, but aliquots of these composites were re-composited to form monthly and quarterly composite samples as well. These composite samples were to be compared with the mathematical averages of concentrations obtained from our regular sampling program at the same station over the same period of time. The regular sampling program produces daily nutrient samples during low-flow intervals, and three nutrient samples per day during high flow periods following storms. Pesticides are sampled twice weekly during low flow between April 15 and August 15, three times daily during high flow in this time period, and once or twice a month during the rest of the year.

Composites were analyzed for both pesticides and nutrients. The basic question being investigated was, "How closely will composite concentrations match the average concentration in the creek, as estimated by the average of discrete samples from the regular program?"

Several factors contributed to the differences between the composite concentrations and the averages of those in the discrete samples. For both pesticides and nutrients, the aliquots for the composite sample were taken on a different schedule than the discrete samples. Since the concentrations in the creek change with time, the composite sample and the average of the discrete samples probably did not contain the same set of concentrations. For pesticides, the concentrations present in some months were low enough that the analytical error was substantial in comparison to the concentration. Both of these factors obscured the comparison we were trying to make, by introducing other sources of difference. For 1992, we revised the evaluation sampling in ways that were designed to minimize these additional sources of difference between the composite concentration and the average of the discrete samples.

During 1992, evaluation sampling was based entirely on our ongoing nutrient sampling program on Rock Creek. A 50 mL aliquot of every sample analyzed during the month was composited, and the composite was analyzed at the end of the month, for comparison with the simple mean of the month's discrete samples. In this way, the chemistry of the water in the composite sample reflected exactly that of the water in the discrete samples. Nitrate and chloride were used for the comparison, because their analytical uncertainty is lowest among the parameters we measure, as compared to their typical concentrations in the environment. The basic question being asked in 1992 was, "How closely will composite concentrations match the average of the concentrations in the discrete samples from which the composites were made?"

Storage stability experiments

Storage stability experiments were performed in both years to evaluate the rate at which alachlor and atrazine would be lost from a sample during storage under refrigeration. For these experiments, a large volume of lake water was obtained from the Sandusky water treatment plant, and spiked with atrazine and alachlor to provide an appropriate concentration. In 1991, 1 ppb of atrazine and 2 ppb of alachlor were added; in 1992, 3 ppb of each were added. The actual concentration in the storage samples was unknown because some alachlor and atrazine may have been present in the lake water. However, the actual concentration is not of concern for these experiments, as long as it is in a reasonable environmental range. What is of concern is the pattern of change of this concentration over time.

After thorough mixing, the large spiked sample was placed into 1 quart glass jars, capped with teflon-lined caps, and placed in refrigerated storage. At the scheduled intervals, a jar was removed from the refrigerator and extracted. Extracts were stored at -10° C prior to analysis. After analysis in the 1992 experiment, the remaining extracts were archived at -10° C for future reference.

In 1991, samples were analyzed weekly for 13 weeks, then every other week for another 26 weeks. The results showed that this schedule was too spread out in time. As a consequence, in 1992 samples were analyzed on days 1 (in duplicate), 2, 4, 7, 10, 14, 21, 28, 35, 42, 56, and 70.

Analysis

Method Summary

The extraction and concentration of the pesticides is based on Section 10A of the U. S. EPA's *Manual of Analytical Methods for the Analysis of Pesticides in Human and Environmental Samples* (EPA-600/8-80-038). This method involves liquid-liquid extraction with methylene chloride and subsequent concentration and transfer to 2-propanol in Kuderna-Danish apparatus and heating blocks.

Dual capillary columns are used to achieve separations of many of the currently used pesticides. Capillary columns provide greatly improved resolution of peaks and sensitivity in comparison with packed columns. Dual columns provide a type of simultaneous confirmation for many of the pesticides, as well as separations of compounds not achievable on a single column.

Nitrogen-phosphorus thermionic detectors are used for both capillary columns. These detectors are highly sensitive to the nitrogen and phosphorus contained within most current generation pesticides but they do not respond to halogens or other moieties to which electron capture detectors are sensitive. The use of the nitrogen-phosphorus detectors reduces the need for time consuming sample clean-up or preliminary separations.

Sample Extraction

Adjustment of sample pH, if necessary, is carried out immediately prior to sample extraction. If the pH is outside the range of 6 to 8, it is brought into that range using a buffer (1M KH_2PO_4 adjusted to pH 7.4 with KOH). The extraction methodology is based on Section 10A of the U.S. EPA's *Manual of Analytical Methods for the Analysis of Pesticides in Human and Environmental Samples* (EPA-600/8-80-038).

Sample volume is determined by weight loss. Each sample and bottle is placed on a Mettler PE 3000 balance and the weight is tared to zero. The sample is then poured into a 2000 mL separatory funnel and the sample bottle is reweighed. The "negative" weight in grams of the empty sample bottle is equivalent to the milliliters of sample transferred to the separatory funnel. This volume is recorded in the sample preparation notebook. This procedure avoids multiple use of a graduated cylinder, is more accurate and less time consuming. The samples are not filtered and contain sediments and solutes present in the source water. Depending on sample size, a 50 to 75 mL aliquot of methylene chloride is added to the separatory funnel, and the sample is shaken for 2 minutes. Then the organic and water phases are allowed to separate.

If an emulsion develops in the separatory funnel, which is often the case when samples contain high concentrations of suspended solids or algal growth, the funnel is immersed in an ultrasonic bath filled with ice water. This procedure is relatively effective in breaking down the emulsion.

The separated organic layer is then passed through a drying column into 300 mL tall form beakers. The drying column is made of an eight inch section of one inch diameter glass tubing. One end is tightly packed with pre-washed Pyrex glass wool, and approximately 30 grams of Na_2SO_4 (previously baked at 600° C) is added and then topped with loosely packed wool. Each column is pre-rinsed with 25 mL of methylene chloride. If an emulsion persists after the sonification, the organic phase is passed through a column packed with loose glass wool only, and then dried.

The extraction process is repeated, along with sonification, if needed. After the second extract is passed through the drying column, the column is rinsed with 25 mL of methylene chloride.

The dried organic extract is transferred into a 500 mL Kuderna-Danish assembly which is fitted with a ten mL graduated concentrator tube. Several fine (20 mesh) trifluoroethylene resin boiling chips are added to the assemblies along with 1 mL of azobenzene (internal reference) in hexane. A three ball Snyder column is added and pre-wetted with 1 mL of 2-propanol prior to being placed on a water bath set at 60° C. When the total volume in the Kuderna-Danish flask is reduced to less than 5 mls., the assembly is removed from the bath and allowed to cool. The concentrator tube is removed and the solvent volume is further reduced to ~.1 mL under N₂ on a heating block at 55 ° C. The concentrator tubes are allowed to cool. Using the graduations on the concentrator tubes, a final sample volume of 1.0 mL is obtained by adding 2-propanol. Samples are mixed on a Vortex-Genie mixer prior to transfer to a 1.8 mL screw cap vial. The vials are capped with a Teflon™ coated septum and refrigerated prior to analysis. Following analysis, new septa are placed on the vials and they are placed in a freezer for long term storage.

All glassware used in the process of sample extraction and concentration is washed in heated, carbon filtered, reverse osmosis treated water containing a detergent. Glassware is then rinsed in the same type of heated water and then rinsed three times with distilled water. Each piece of glassware then receives a final acetone rinse. Sample vials are pre-rinsed with acetone, dried and capped prior to use. The glass wool is washed for 12 hours via soxhlet extraction with methylene chloride and the sodium sulfate baked at 600° C for 12 hours prior to use.

Twenty sets of glassware are available for the extractions. Typically, environmental and quality control samples are set up for processing in batches of 20. One or two such batches can be processed per day by the laboratory staff.

2-propanol (isopropyl alcohol) was chosen as the solvent for two reasons. It does dissolve all the compounds of interest without the use of other solvents. Thus its use facilitates the preparation of mixed standards containing multiple pesticides. Furthermore, it is suitable for LC work in aqueous organic solvent systems. The same extracts can be used for LC confirmation, when possible.

Analytical Procedures

The primary analytical system used for these analyses consists of a Varian 3400 gas chromatograph equipped with two N-P detectors and a Varian 8035 autosampler. The sample (3.0 μ L) is slowly injected (.1 μ L/sec) into a piece of 1/4 inch capillary barometer tubing ~5"

long which serves as an injection tube. The end of the tube has a stainless steel 1/4 to 1/16" reducing fitting through which two capillary columns are inserted until the ends of the columns are 1 cm below the end of the injection needle, when it is fully inserted into the injector tube.

Several capillary columns are suitable for these analyses. We have tested the following columns: DB1, DB5, DB1701, carbowax, durawax, and SP1000. We are currently using a DB1701 column and a DB5 column. These columns were chosen because of their ability to resolve several groups of compounds that are of interest but are difficult to separate. These include atrazine-simazine-carbofuran, metolachlor-malathion, and chlorpyrifos-cyanazine. The columns are 30 m x .32 mm and have a 1 μ film thickness. By inserting both columns in the same injector, simultaneous confirmation of 20-24 compounds can be achieved for each sample. In some samples the number of peaks recognized by the data system may exceed 200 per column.

Temperature programming is used to optimize separations and total run time. Typical temperatures and programming are listed below:

injector - 200°
detector - 300°
initial column temperature 90° C;
hold 2 min;
ramp to 130° C at 10° C per min;
ramp to 230° C at 1.4° C per min;
hold for 1min;
ramp to 275° C at 25° per min;
hold 5 min.
(the entire run takes 78 min)

The data system (Varian DS 654) is interfaced to the GC and the autosampler and controls both in the automated mode. Peaks are identified by corrected retention times (correct for the actual retention time of azobenzene) within a 12 second window (~1.3% at 30 min).

The data system is connected to the VAX 11/750. The reports from the individual channels are transferred with identification to the VAX. The reports include peak names, where identified, or number for non-identified peaks, concentrations, peak time, time offset where peak is identified, peak area, type of area calculation, and peak width at half height.

Calibration Procedure

Pesticide reference standards of known purity are obtained from the Analytical Chemistry Branch of USEPA. Pesticide breakdown products are normally obtained from the manufacturers. Stock solutions are made by weighing, to the nearest 0.01 mg, approximately

12.5 mg of sample into a glass container and by dissolving it in an appropriate volume of 2-propanol to produce a 500 mg/L standard. The stock containers are capped, solvent level marked and the container placed in the freezer. Dilutions of individual pesticides or breakdown products are chromatographed to determine retention times for each column and check for impurities. A mixed standard, at concentrations of either 1 or 5 mg/L, depending on detector response and anticipated environmental concentrations, is made from the stock solutions and used the calibration standard and as reference standards.

The automatic sampler for the GC contains positions for 60 sample vials (four trays with 15 positions each). For routine analyses the tray protocol is as follows:

calibration standard
rinse
reference standard
rinse
10 samples, each followed by a rinse
reference standard
rinse
10 samples, each followed by a rinse
reference standard
rinse
solvent blank

(total positions used = 49)

The initial calibration standard is used to update the calibration values in the data system. The remaining standards are treated as reference standards. The three reference standards are treated by the data system as normal environmental samples and, consequently their actual concentrations, as calculated by the data system, are printed out directly on the data system report. Comparing the reported concentrations in the reference standards with the expected concentrations provides a quick method of tracking the performance of the analytical system.

A separate rinse vial, containing the solvent, is used between every standard and sample vial. This provides an extra rinse between each standard or sample, beyond that provided by the standard rinsing features of the automatic sample changer.

Data Storage and Processing Procedures

Every sample and every standard (both calibration and reference) has a sequential computer identification number (CID). A preset list of CIDs and corresponding tray and vial numbers is used both to position the vials in the automatic sampler trays initially and to check that the vials were in the proper position at the conclusion of the run. Following the analytical

run, new septa are placed on the vials and they are transferred to a freezer for storage as archived samples.

The original chromatographs and the reports for each channel comprise the "hard copy" original documentation of the results for each analysis. These copies are organized in CID order for each year and are stored in files. The individual reports contain the CID numbers as well as the tray and vial number and the date and time of analysis. The reports are automatically transferred into the VAX 11/750 computer as soon as they are generated by the data system. The reports are also temporarily stored on disk drives of the GC data system.

Data analysis

Analytical results are automatically transferred from the GC data system to the WQL's VAX 11/750 minicomputer, where they are stored in several custom-written databases developed within the VAX program DATATRIEVE. From there, subsets can be moved into ASCII files for analysis, interpretation, and transfer to other computer environments, particular the WQL's Macintosh cluster.

The results of the study were subjected to various forms of exploratory and confirmatory analysis and graphical display, mostly using commercially available software including Data Desk, Excel, and Cricket Graph, available for Macintosh computer systems. Several custom pieces of software were written to facilitate data analysis, or were already available in the WQL, including software to calculate various kinds of average concentrations for river samples and to transfer data between various storage compartments.

In addition to simple means of concentrations, two weighted means are often calculated for WQL data, which are samples of a continuous process which varies over time, and, for river samples, with changing flow. These are the time-weighted mean (TWMC) and the flow-weighted mean (FWMC), which are defined as

$$\text{TWMC} = \frac{\sum_i c_i t_i}{\sum_i t_i} \quad \text{and} \quad \text{FWMC} = \frac{\sum_i c_i q_i t_i}{\sum_i q_i t_i}$$

where c_i is the concentration in sample i , q_i is the flow at the time sample i is taken, and t_i is the time which sample i represents. If sampling occurred at fixed frequencies, then the TWMC would be equal to the simple, unweighted mean. However, since we sample more frequently during high flow than during low flow periods, we need to time-weight our calculations to prevent biasing our averages toward high flow periods. The flow-weighted concentration takes

account of the fact that more water goes by the station during high flow than during low flow. It is appropriate for estimating loading rates, and is often used when the focus of the study is on interactions between lakes and their tributaries. The time-weighted concentration ignores the amount of water going by the station, and is appropriate for questions of exposure to animals and plants living in the water at the sampling site, or to humans withdrawing water (at a more or less constant rate) for a drinking water source.

For this study, the FWMC is generally not of interest. For the comparisons between composite samples and averages of discrete samples, TWMCs are appropriate for the 1991 comparison and simple averages are appropriate for the 1992 comparison. For the composite samples from Lake Erie, simple averages (means or medians) are appropriate as measures of yearlong concentrations. Boxplots are also used to provide graphic summaries of data distributions.

RESULTS

Operational analysis

Data reflecting the success of the sampling operation are shown in Figures 2 and 3. Based on the calendars returned from the water treatment plants, water supply plant personnel were conscientious about taking the daily aliquots, and few scheduled aliquots were missed. Some decline in performance was noted toward the end of the project, however. Autosamplers also performed reliably.

Samples from the Toledo water system were initially taken cooperatively by Sisters at a nunnery. The reliability of sampling was considerably lower here than at the other stations. Sampling was then handed over to a high-school student who had earlier expressed an interest in our programs. The student's reliability record was excellent. These observations suggest that it may be unwise to rely on a group to perform composite sampling. While verification is impossible, the group's relatively poor performance may have been the result of a failure to adequately schedule who would take what sample when and where, a problem which does not exist when a single person is designated as the local cooperator.

Two samples were lost in shipment. Considering that the program involved 312 samples, this is a pretty good record. Many samples lost some volume due to leakage during shipping, but in most cases the volume lost appeared to be minimal, and in no case was the remaining volume inadequate for extraction and analysis.

To a degree which we had not anticipated, shipping of samples to the lab and of empty bottles to the cooperators is expensive. These shipments were a major expense of the project. In part, this was because of the need to have the samples come promptly, which required using second-day air express. Shipments across the border with Canada were particularly problematic - they were often delayed for as much as a week, at customs and at exchanges between Canadian and U.S. shipping agents, and expenses involved in shipping a full bottle to the WQL and an empty replacement to the cooperator were often nearly twice the cost of analyzing the sample. Shipping charges were quite unpredictable, varying from month to month even though the contents shipped were nearly identical. Most of this variability seems to be due to inconsistent assignment of shipping charges by the shipping company, not to differences in the mode of shipping (e.g. first-day vs. second-day service).

Figure 2. The reliability of volunteer cooperators in taking the scheduled daily aliquots. The data for the minimum percent received are drawn from all cooperators, and no one cooperator was consistently the least reliable.

Figure 3. Reliability of cooperative samplers, as reflected by the number of calendars and samples received. Since one station used an autosampler and had no calendar, a perfect month has 13 samples and 12 calendars.

Storage stability experiments

The 1991 experiment was marred by several problems in its design and implementation. The second sample, which in retrospect was probably the most important sample for defining the storage behavior, was lost due to a sample preparation error, as was the fourth sample. The atrazine concentration was sufficiently low that analytical error masked possible declines in concentration. The graph of the resulting data (Figure 4) suggests that time intervals between analyses were too large to resolve concentration declines during storage, and that changes occurred primarily during the first four weeks, if at all. No definitive conclusions could be drawn from this experiment, except that the experiment needed to be re-designed and re-run.

Figure 4. Results of the 1991 storage stability experiment.

Drawing on this experience, the 1992 storage stability experiment was designed with short storage intervals at the beginning of the experiment, when most of the change was expected. The results of the 1992 experiment are shown in Figure 5. The plot on the left shows concentrations of atrazine and alachlor as a function of time. Alachlor concentrations decrease with time, especially after about day 20, while atrazine concentrations fluctuate within the range of analytical error, but show no clear trend throughout the study period. Some of the fluctuations in both alachlor and atrazine concentrations are artifacts of using a multipoint calibration. In the right plot, these fluctuations are smoothed out by plotting the peak areas rather than the

concentrations, and by plotting the ratio of alachlor to atrazine peak areas rather than plotting each separately. If we assume atrazine does not change during the period of the experiment, as is indicated by the left plot, then alachlor declines steadily from an initial concentration about half again as large as atrazine to a final concentration about one-quarter that of atrazine. The loss of alachlor over a 30 day period is substantial, amounting to about half the original concentration.

Figure 5. 1992 storage stability experiment results.

Evaluation of Composite Sampling

The goal of composite sampling is to avoid the high cost of repeated sampling which is normally required to obtain a reliable average concentration for a substance in a time-variant environment. Instead of analyzing multiple discrete samples and averaging their concentrations, the averaging is done physically during the accumulation of the composite sample, and only one analysis is required. Thus a realistic way to evaluate composite sampling is to see how close the concentration in the composite comes to matching the average of the concentrations in the discrete samples of which the composite is composed. Furthermore, the analytical cost of the composite sample is identical to that of any single discrete sample which might have been taken during the compositing period, and which would have been used to represent the period under a discrete sampling program with the same analytical budget. Thus it is appropriate to consider the degree of match in the context of the range of values which occurred during the compositing period. Comparisons of this sort are presented for 1991 data in Figures 6 to 8, and for 1992 data in Figures 9 to 11.

Figure 6 displays graphs of the difference between the composite concentration and the TWMC obtained from the WQL's regular discrete sampling program. In 1991, the aliquots for the weekly composite samples were not taken on the same schedule as the discrete samples. Thus differences between composite sample and TWMC incorporate differences due to the sampling schedule as well as differences due to the sampling methodologies. In spite of this extra source of difference, all nitrate differences are less than 0.5 mg/L, and all chloride differences except one are less than 5 mg/L. These are less than 5% of the range of values seen during at least one week of the experiment. This level of comparability is very good for environmental measurements.

The one chloride data point which involves a difference of about 11 mg/L was obtained from a week during which the regular sampling program suffered a failure and only obtained samples on three of seven days, whereas the compositing sampler performed according to schedule. During the course of the week, flows changed substantially, indicating that a runoff event was occurring. Runoff events produce predictable changes in both chloride and nitrate concentrations. Thus the comparatively large difference during this week is due to changes in concentrations over the course of the week, which were sampled very differently by the two sampling programs. Nitrate does not show a similar high difference because this week occurred during a time of year when the nitrate concentrations are relatively low and stable with changes in flow.

Figure 6. Difference between mean concentration and composite concentration in the context of the concentration range during the compositing period.

Figures 7 and 8 present the same data as Figure 6, but as a function of time. Comparisons among these figures show that the differences between composite concentration and TWMC remain fairly comparable from week to week, and are not obviously affected by changes in the average concentration or in the range of concentrations. During the summer weeks the composite nitrate concentrations are systematically slightly higher than the TWMCs (weeks 12-22; week 0 of the compositing program corresponds to early April). The explanation for this pattern is not clear.

Figure 7. Nitrate concentrations (dots), averages (diamonds) and composite concentrations (circles). 1991 data.

Figure 8. Nitrate concentrations (dots), averages (diamonds) and composite concentrations (circles). 1991 data.

For 1992, the composite sampling evaluation program involved an exact match between the discrete samples and the composite sample. For each discrete sample analyzed as part of the regular sampling program at Rock Creek, a small aliquot was held aside and added to a monthly composite. This approach eliminated the differences due to sampling schedule which were present in the 1991 data, and permitted the composite concentration to be compared to the simple mean of the discrete concentrations. An additional difference between the two years is that the compositing period was one week in 1991 and one month in 1992.

The results of the 1992 composite sampling evaluation program are presented in Figures 9 to 11. The magnitudes of differences between composite concentrations and means of discrete concentrations are comparable to those seen in 1991, suggesting that the non-parallel sampling patterns in 1991 did not, on average, reduce the level of comparability. However, the 1992 data show a weak but definite tendency for the difference between the composite concentration and the mean of the discrete concentrations to increase as a function of the range of concentrations during the compositing period.

For both chloride and nitrate during 1992, the differences were often smaller in relation to the ranges than was true in 1991. To some extent, this reflects the fact that 1992 was a wetter year. Hence there were more runoff events, and correspondingly more frequent changes in concentration. In addition, the longer compositing period during 1992 provided more opportunity for concentration fluctuations within the compositing period, which tended to increase concentration ranges.

Figure 9. Differences between composite concentrations and means of concentrations in corresponding discrete samples, for 1992.

For nitrate, composite concentrations were higher than discrete sample means in 5 of the 12 months. Since the differences are relatively small, and differences in the same direction are not grouped together in succeeding months, the direction (or sign) of the difference does not appear to be significant.

Figure 10. Composite sampling results for nitrate, 1992 program. Two composite symbols are shown for January because the January composite sample was analyzed in duplicate.

For chloride, composite concentrations are lower than the corresponding means of discrete samples in 11 of 12 months. The cause of this result is unclear. If it is reproducible in other composite sampling evaluations, it indicates a small low bias for composited samples for chloride.

It is useful to compare these differences between composite sample concentrations and the averages of corresponding discrete samples with the differences in concentration between replicate pairs of samples, which are gathered as a regular part of our quality control programs.

Figure 11. Composite sampling results for chloride, 1992 program.

The difference between replicate pairs is often taken as a measure of the precision of the measurement process, including sample collection, processing, and analysis. Thus the distribution of these differences reflects the distribution of error in the measurement process. If the compositing process physically creates an average concentration identical to the average concentration calculated from discrete samples, then the distribution of differences between composite and average should be the same as that for measurements on replicate pairs.

This comparison is made in Figure 12. Differences in concentration for 290 replicate samples are compared with those from the 1991 and 1992 compositing programs. The data are sorted by increasing concentration, and plotted on a percentile axis in order to keep the span of each set of data the same, in spite of different numbers of observations. Since most of the differences are small compared to the largest few differences, the data are plotted on a vertical logarithmic scale for better display. These plots show that, for both nitrate and chloride, composite/average differences are generally somewhat higher than replicate differences, except

at the high end of the concentrations where the replicate differences tend to be larger. The pattern at the high end is probably an artifact of the much larger sample size for the replicate pairs, and the correspondingly greater likelihood of encountering examples drawn from the extremes of the distribution.

The tendency of replicate differences to be smaller than composite/average differences reflects the extra sources of difference which are involved when the comparison is between a composite sample and 15 to 30 discrete sample analyses, as opposed to two identical analyses of two water samples taken in different bottles but at the same time, and is an expected consequence of the additivity of variances. While this comparison shows that compositing involves some additional error beyond that attributable to the discrete sample measurement process, this additional error is small in the context of the environmental range, and small compared to the basic measurement process error over most of the range of the distribution.

Figure 12. Differences between composites and averages compared with differences between replicate samples. The line represents differences from 290 replicated samples taken between 1989 and 1991. Diamonds represent differences from the 1991 composite program. Circles represent differences from the 1992 composite program.

Composite sampling of Lake Erie drinking water

Results of the composite sampling program at the 13 Lake Erie drinking water plants are shown in Figures 13 to 17, one for each pesticide. In each figure, the bottom graph is a box plot summary of the concentrations observed, by station. The correspondence between station names as shown in Figure 1 and the station numbers used in these graphs is as follows:

<u>Station Number</u>	<u>Station Name</u>
1	Dunkirk, NY
2	Erie, PA
3	Lake County, Ohio
4	Cleveland (Baldwin)
5	Lorain
5.1	Lorain raw water sample (1992 only)
6	Sandusky
7	Port Clinton
8	Oak Harbor
9	Toledo
10	Monroe, MI
11	Union, Ontario
12	Elgin, Ontario
13	Nanticoke, Ontario

The bottom graph in each figure is divided by a somewhat arbitrarily placed horizontal line which separates the highest concentrations observed from the remaining concentrations. The upper left graph is a bar graph of the number of samples per station, with raw and finished water samples lumped together for Lorain. The shaded (white) portion of the bars corresponds to the high values from the lower graph. The upper right graph is a similar bar graph, but showing samples per month, starting with month 1 in January 1991. Again the shaded portion of the bars corresponds to the high values from the lower graph. These three graphs together give a visual summary of the overall concentration patterns, and indicate when and where relatively high concentrations were observed.

Concentration patterns for atrazine

Figure 13. Concentrations of atrazine observed in samples at Lake Erie drinking water plants during the two years of the study.

Concentration patterns for alachlor

Figure 14. Concentrations of alachlor observed in samples at Lake Erie drinking water plants during the two years of the study.

Concentration patterns for metolachlor

Figure 15. Concentrations of metolachlor observed in samples at Lake Erie drinking water plants during the two years of the study.

Concentration patterns for metribuzin

Figure 16. Concentrations of metribuzin observed in samples at Lake Erie drinking water plants during the two years of the study.

Concentration patterns for simazine

Figure 17. Concentrations of simazine observed in samples at Lake Erie drinking water plants during the two years of the study.

DISCUSSION

Operator reliability

In general, water treatment plant personnel and other cooperators took samples reliably, and many were interested in the results of the project. Some decline in reliability occurred toward the end of the two year study, however. In addition, samples were not taken on weekend days at some plants because personnel were not there. The autosampler installed in the Monroe plant worked without problems during the span of the study.

The aliquots missed by the cooperators probably did not have a major impact on our estimates of Lake Erie pesticide concentrations. Nonetheless, using an autosampler for compositing is probably preferable, especially in long-term studies, or in highly variable environments, where a single missed aliquot could have a large effect on the monthly concentration. In addition, an autosampler can be set to take hourly aliquots as easily as daily, which permits even better coverage of a temporally varying concentration.

On the other hand, autosamplers are expensive to purchase, but cooperators are free. Some mechanism is needed to be sure the autosampler is functioning properly, whether it is an electronic monitor which is part of a computer-driven autosampler, or a local volunteer who will call and report that the autosampler is malfunctioning. There is also some educational value to involving local cooperators in sample collection, because their curiosity is aroused, and they are interested to learn what "their" project is discovering.

Our one experience with local cooperation by committee was not very successful, probably because it was not sufficiently clear who would be in charge of making sure aliquots were collected according to schedule.

Compositing as a "physical averaging" process

In general, the evaluation sampling showed good agreement between composite concentrations and the discrete samples they were compared with. For chloride in 1992, there was an indication of a minor systematic difference between the composite and the average. However, the difference was small compared to the range of values in the discrete samples. The goal of compositing is to obtain a good estimate of the average concentration without incurring the cost of multiple analyses. In this context, the appropriate question is whether the composite sample is confidently closer to the average than a randomly chosen discrete sample. Clearly this is the case.

In certain instances, however, composite sampling is not useful. The compounds of interest must remain unchanged in concentration (no evaporation or chemical conversion to other compounds) during the period of storage, otherwise compositing will give a biased estimate of the average concentration (see below). If one or more compound of interest is not stable over the desired compositing time interval, compositing must be considered very carefully on a case-by-case basis, to balance the disadvantage of a known biasing factor which cannot be corrected for against the advantage of damping environmental variability.

Also, the main source of uncertainty in the average concentration one is seeking to characterize must be environmental fluctuations rather than operational factors such as analytical error. When concentrations are low relative to the working range of the analytical equipment, so that the relative error due to analytical uncertainty is large, or when concentrations in the environment do not fluctuate very much, compositing may offer no advantage over analyzing a single discrete sample. At the same time, compositing would not appear to offer a disadvantage, except for the slight additional effort involved relative to taking a single discrete sample.

Effects of storage

Data shown in the right panel of Figure 5 indicate that alachlor decays steadily during refrigerated storage. The data also allow a decay rate for alachlor to be calculated, assuming that atrazine remains constant. Under this assumption, we get

$$C_t = C_o 10^{-0.011t}$$

where C_t is the concentration after t days and C_o is the initial concentration. The r^2 value of 0.991 indicates a very good fit between the data and this formula.

A little algebra leads to an alternative formula giving the percent of the original compound remaining at time t :

$$P_t = 100 \cdot 10^{-0.011t}$$

This formula leads to the following short table of alachlor remaining after storage for varying lengths of time:

Table 2. Percent of alachlor remaining in sample as a function of storage time, based on 1992 storage stability experiments.

Storage time in days:	1	3	7	10	14	21	30
Percent alachlor remaining:	97	93	84	78	70	59	47

The rate of decay in other samples might be quite different, as a result of differences in initial concentration, storage history, and "matrix effects": the unknown chemical and perhaps bacterial constituents of the sample.

This relationship cannot be applied in a simple fashion to composite samples, because the aliquot from the last day will have been stored for only a few days, and most of its alachlor will remain. The aliquot from the first day will have been stored for about 30 days, and about half its alachlor will be gone.

As a general guideline, if we assume that the alachlor in each aliquot is equal, then the percent remaining after a month of storage will be approximately equal to that for the average storage time, which is about 16 days, corresponding to about 67% remaining. However, it should be remembered that the potential value of composite sampling lies in its ability to deal with an environment where the concentrations are **not** constant over time. The more the concentrations fluctuate, the more useful composite sampling is, but the more impossible it is to adjust for the effects of loss on storage, because by definition we do not know which days had high concentrations and which days had low concentrations.

These results show that an alternative compositing strategy is needed for alachlor; one which preserves the sample from breakdown prior to analysis. If no such strategy can be found which is also cost effective, compositing may still be preferable to infrequent discrete sampling in some circumstances, but the tradeoffs are much more complex, and must be evaluated in the context of a particular sampling program's goals.

Distribution of concentrations

All observed concentrations are low, compared to concentrations routinely observed in rivers during the use season. Of the five herbicides for which data are presented, atrazine is the one most consistently detected. The most frequent detections and the highest concentrations are observed in the Western Basin of Lake Erie, and in the months of June, July, and August. Metolachlor is frequently detected, and is characteristically present at higher concentrations in the Western Basin, and especially at the Monroe station, than elsewhere. Metolachlor is present year-round at the Monroe station, but detections elsewhere are seasonal or sporadic. Alachlor, metribuzin, and cyanazine are only occasionally detected at any station. More of the detections occur at Western Basin stations than at those in the Central and Eastern Basins.

Several factors explain the higher frequency of detections of herbicides in the Western Basin. Most of the Lake Erie drainage basin's land area drains into rivers which enter the Western Basin. Furthermore, a higher percentage of the Western Basin land area is devoted to

row crop agriculture where these compounds are used. Finally, the water volume of the Western Basin is smaller compared to the tributary inflow, and the Western Basin tributaries carry higher concentrations of herbicides on average than do those of the Eastern and Central Basins.

Many of the detections of the herbicides other than atrazine occurred in January and February of 1991. 1990 was a wet year, with average or above average rainfall every month. The runoff in major Ohio tributaries to Lake Erie during the period December 1990 - February 1991 was nearly equivalent to the average annual discharge. Apparently, these conditions led to mobilization of agricultural chemicals and their transport into the lake during the high flow periods which followed the rainfall.

Distribution of the higher herbicide concentrations

Although all herbicide concentrations in all samples were relatively low in comparison to concentrations seen in many tributaries and inland lakes and reservoirs, it is instructive to examine the temporal and spatial distribution of the highest observed values. Patterns in these values may suggest times or places where exceedences of health guidelines are most likely to occur.

Atrazine

"High concentrations" of atrazine were defined as those above 0.25 ppb. While most concentrations of atrazine were fairly low, atrazine was more consistently observed at measurable levels than the other herbicides. Atrazine reached its highest values, and had the most frequent values above the cutoff, at stations 6 - 9, located in the Western Basin of Lake Erie. Concentrations above the cutoff were more frequent in June, July, and August of each year, but were also observed in January and February of 1991, a result which would not have been anticipated based on concentration patterns in rivers (Richards and Baker, 1993).

Alachlor

High concentrations for alachlor were defined as those above 0.2 ppb. These concentrations were observed mostly at the Western Basin stations. They occurred mostly in the first two months of the study, January and February 1991. While none of the sample concentrations exceeded the MCL of 2.0 ppb, concentrations in two samples of about 1.6 and 1.4 ppb were closer to the alachlor MCL than those in any sample for any of the other pesticides. In large part, this reflects the relatively low MCL for alachlor (Table 3).

Metolachlor

High concentrations for metolachlor were defined as those above 0.5 ppb. These concentrations occurred more frequently during January and February 1991 than in other months, but were spread throughout the study period. The great majority of these higher concentrations occurred at the Monroe station, which clearly stands out from all the rest in the boxplot in Figure 15. GC/MS analysis of several of these samples confirms that the quantified compound is indeed metolachlor, and not some other compound which happens to pass through the gas chromatograph at the same speed as metolachlor. This pattern, the frequent occurrence of relatively high values of just one herbicide at just one station, cannot easily be explained by appeal to non-point source runoff from Lake Erie tributaries. It is suggestive of a point source of contamination somewhere in the vicinity of the Monroe station. No further interpretation of this pattern can be offered at the present time.

Metribuzin

High concentrations for metolachlor were defined as those above 0.1 ppb. Nearly all of these high concentrations occurred during the early months of the study. They occurred mostly at the Western Basin stations, though at least one of these high concentrations occurred at 9 of the 13 stations. None exceeded 1.0 ppb.

Simazine

Higher concentrations for metolachlor were defined as those above 0.05 ppb. Most of them occurred during September and October 1991, and there is no station pattern. No concentration exceeded 0.5 ppb. Given the lack of a station pattern, the infrequent occurrence of simazine at other times, and the fact that these "high" concentrations are really quite low, these observations may be artifacts of the analytical process rather than true observations of simazine in Lake Erie drinking water.

Significance of the herbicide concentrations for human health

To put the observed herbicide concentrations in a proper perspective, it is necessary to review the approaches used by the U.S. EPA to establish health guidelines. It is particularly important to understand what the health guidelines mean.

HALs, MCLs, and human health

The U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) has developed standard procedures to evaluate the health hazards associated with ingesting pesticides and other compounds. If direct

evidence of human health effects is lacking (as is usually the case), the evaluation relies on tests carried out using laboratory animals. From these tests and other available information, the EPA establishes a series of health advisory levels (HALs), which are concentrations in drinking water at which adverse health effects would not be expected to occur from exposure for the specified length of time. As the name indicates, HALs are advisory.

Health Advisory Levels for the five herbicides discussed here are given in Table 3; their derivation is described in detail in EPA (1989). HALs are generally derived from laboratory animal studies, and are based on the lowest concentration at which any effect of ingesting atrazine could be detected in the most sensitive species tested, which is called the Lowest Observed Adverse Effect Level or LOAEL. The next lower concentration tested, at which no effect was observed, is called the No Observed Adverse Effect Level or NOAEL. Somewhere between these two concentrations is the threshold concentration, below which adverse effects do not occur. To determine the lifetime HAL for a substance, the NOAEL dose rate (in mg/kg/day) is divided by a large safety factor (1000 in the case of atrazine) and converted to a drinking water concentration by assuming that a person weighs 70 kg and drinks two liters of water per day, and that 20% of a person's intake of the substance comes from drinking water. Since most non-occupational exposure to the herbicides of interest is thought to come from drinking water, the 20% assumption provides an additional safety factor which approaches five-fold for these compounds. Similar approaches are used for calculating HALs for shorter exposure periods.

COMPOUND	HALs					MCL	Safety Factor	Cancer Class
	1 day (child)	10 day (child)	7 year (child)	7 year (adult)	70 year (adult)			
Atrazine	100	100	50	200	3	3.0	1000	C
Alachlor	100	100	-	-	-	2.0	-	B2
Metolachlor	2000	2000	2000	5000	100	-	1000	C
Metribuzin	5000	5000	300	900	200	-	100	D
Simazine	70	70	70	70	4	4.0	1000	C

Table 3. HALs, MCLs, safety factors, and carcinogenicity rankings for the herbicides of interest. Units for HALs and MCLs are ppb (or $\mu\text{g/L}$). Cancer classes: B2, probable human carcinogen, based on animal studies; C, possible human carcinogen; D, unclassified; evidence lacking or insufficient.

In addition to HALs, the EPA may also establish a Maximum Contaminant Level (MCL) for a substance under authority of the federal Safe Drinking Water Act. MCLs are legally enforceable drinking water standards based on an assumed lifetime exposure, and are the standards to which a water utility's average concentrations will be compared.

The EPA also classifies compounds according to the form of health risk they represent and the degree of certainty associated with the health risk. An additional tenfold safety factor was included in the lifetime HAL because EPA ranks atrazine as a Class C (possible) carcinogen.

The interpretation of the MCL as a risk factor for human health varies somewhat depending on the classification of the compound as a potential carcinogen. For class C compounds, the MCL is a concentration which an adult could consume at the rate of 2 liters per day for 70 years without incurring any increased risk of adverse health consequences. For class B carcinogens, the MCL is a concentration which corresponds to an increased cancer risk of approximately one in a million, if the compound is ingested in drinking water at that concentration at 2 liters per day for 70 years.

The most important point is that MCLs are designed to keep risks very low, and that they are based on very long term exposure. Short term exposures must be at much higher concentrations before they represent a human health risk, as is reflected in the higher HALs for short-term exposure. Concentrations as high as these short term HALs are rarely observed even in tributaries draining agricultural watersheds.

Composite sample concentrations and their human health implications

No herbicide in any composite sample taken during this study exceeded any of its short-term or lifetime HALs. Several samples of alachlor came nearest to exceeding the lifetime HAL, and considering the demonstrated loss on storage of alachlor, the true average concentration in the drinking water for these months and stations might have exceeded the lifetime HAL. The annual averages for all compounds would clearly be less than their respective lifetime HALs. Thus the results of this study indicate that no significant adverse health effects are to be expected from exposure to herbicides through Lake Erie drinking water, unless concentrations increase substantially in the future.

Agricultural land use is more predominant in the Lake Erie basin than in any other Great Lakes drainage basin. Thus the results of this study can be tentatively extended to the other Great Lakes as well. It seems very unlikely that adverse health effects will occur as a result of herbicide exposure through drinking water drawn from any of the Great Lakes. The limited data available from other studies support this conclusion as well.

This conclusion, however, cannot be blindly extended to those whose drinking water is drawn from inland sources within the Great Lakes drainage basin. Inland lakes and reservoirs, rivers, and even local groundwater resources often have higher concentrations of herbicides than were found in Lake Erie. Most locations which have been adequately characterized do have

long-term average concentrations which are below the lifetime HALs, but many locations are poorly characterized. At many of these locations, concentrations fluctuate much more widely and rapidly than they do at locations in the Great Lakes. These are the ideal places at which to employ composite sampling, at least for compounds which are stable under storage.

The effect of carbon treatment on herbicide concentrations

Baker (1985) presented indirect evidence of herbicide removal by granular activated carbon filtration at Fremont, Ohio, where the water source is the Sandusky River. Miltner et al. (1989) demonstrated the effectiveness of removing herbicides from drinking water using powdered activated carbon. During 1992, we attempted a small investigation of the effectiveness of granular activated carbon filtration in removing herbicides from Lake Erie water, where concentrations are much lower than in the Sandusky River. At the Lorain WTP, composite samples were taken of both raw and finished water, from February through December. The results are shown in Figure 18.

Figure 18. Atrazine in raw and finished water at the Lorain water treatment plant, 1992.

Only atrazine and metolachlor were detected in raw or finished water, and only one raw water sample contained detectable metolachlor. The low concentrations and relatively few detections limit the value of the results of this experiment. However, at least for atrazine, carbon filtration did successfully lower the herbicide concentration even from initially low levels less than .25 ppb, as is shown in Figure 18.

CONCLUSIONS

1. Composite sampling programs can be successfully operated either by volunteer cooperators or by autosamplers.
2. Compositing provides an economical means to obtain a concentration which is in excellent agreement with the average concentration which would have been obtained from separate analyses of each aliquot of the composite sample.
3. Compositing is not useful if the compound of interest breaks down significantly during storage over the compositing interval. Atrazine does not break down during one month storage, but alachlor shows substantial losses during one month.
4. If concentrations are low and not very variable, analytical uncertainty may be the major source of analytical error, rather than temporal fluctuations in the environment. In this case, compositing may not reduce the uncertainty associated with an average concentration. Multiple analyses of either discrete or composite samples, or an improved analytical methodology, may be the only way to reduce uncertainty in this case.
5. Concentrations of alachlor, atrazine, metolachlor, metribuzin, and simazine are consistently low in finished drinking water drawn from Lake Erie, both as compared to health standards for these compounds and as compared to concentrations observed in some rivers and inland lakes in the Lake Erie drainage basin. No herbicide in any sample exceeded the MCL or lifetime HAL for any of these herbicides. Average concentrations over the two-year period for all compounds were well below the health guidelines, in most cases by at least an order of magnitude. These results indicate that no adverse health effect is to be expected from exposure to these herbicides in drinking water from Lake Erie, even over a lifetime. This result probably applies to the other Great Lakes as well.
6. Concentrations are generally highest in the summer and early fall months following herbicide application to crops, and following periods of extended heavy rainfall, such as occurred in late 1990 and early 1991.
7. Concentrations are generally highest at the Western Basin stations, which are in closest proximity to the land areas where most of the herbicides are applied.
8. Concentrations of metolachlor at the Monroe station are anomalously (but not dangerously) high. This pattern is confined to one station and one herbicide, and is suggestive of

a nearby persistent point source of metolachlor. Though the observed concentrations do not represent a health hazard, further investigation and possibly mitigation are warranted.

9. A granular carbon filter at the Lorain plant successfully lowered atrazine concentrations in finished water compared to raw water concentrations, even though the raw water concentrations were very low to start with.

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